

not risk-free. Ongoing essays aim to clarify these effects, examining how these particles influence overall cell function.

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3.17.P-Tu303 Biopolymers: Ecotoxicological Risks of Micro and Nanoplastics Aquatic Organisms

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Intense plastic production and poor waste management are promoting the widespread accumulation of microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) in aquatic ecosystems. These size fractions, that disperse through the water column, sediments and biofilms, display high mobility, environmental persistence, and bioavailability, enabling uptake by diverse aquatic taxa, ranging from plankton to higher trophic levels (e.g. fish and humans). The reported effects on aquatic organisms include feeding disruption, oxidative stress, inflammation, metabolic dysregulation, and reproductive impairment. The reported effects on aquatic organisms include feeding disruption, oxidative stress, inflammation, metabolic dysregulation, and reproductive impairment. NPs, due to their small size, ability to penetrate cells, form eco-coronas, and facilitate co-transport of sorbed contaminants, are considered potentially more hazardous to biota.

Biopolymers such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and polylactic acid (PLA), derived from renewable, biological feedstocks, are increasingly proposed as sustainable alternatives to fossil-based polymers. Although expected to degrade in the environment, their degradation rates remain highly context dependent, and environmental fragmentation can still generate micro- and nano-sized particles. As industry moves toward nanoscale formulations, nano-biopolymers introduce new exposure pathways for freshwater organisms. The available studies on nano-biopolymers have reported size- and surface-dependent uptake, interactions with epithelial and digestive tissues, and potential oxidative or inflammatory responses. Critical knowledge gaps persist regarding environmental transformation, environmental levels, biodegradation kinetics and trophic transfer potential of nano-biopolymers in freshwater ecosystems. Furthermore, comparative ecotoxicological data on nano-biopolymers relative to synthetic NPs remain scarce. This study aims to synthesize available evidence on the ecotoxicological impacts of nano-biopolymers in freshwater organisms and evaluate if these polymers are in fact safer and more sustainable than conventional fossil-based.

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3.17.P-Tu304 Understanding Life-Stage Susceptibility to Biodegradable Nanoplastics: A Case Study in *Hediste diversicolor*

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Biodegradable polymers have been proposed as more alternatives to conventional plastics. However, growing evidence suggests that their fragmentation into micro- and nanoplastics (NPs) raising significant concern about potential ecological risks. Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), a prominent biopolymer of the polyhydroxyalkanoate family, can generate NPs whose effects on key aquatic organisms remain poorly understood. This study investigated the impacts of PHB NPs exposure on juvenile and adult polychaete *Hediste diversicolor*, a key bioturbator species in estuarine ecosystems. Organisms were exposed for 14 days to sediments spiked with PHB NPs (103.9 ± 5.07 nm) at 0, 0.5, 2, 8, 32, 128 mg PHB/kg sediment. Behavioral (feeding, burrowing, light